

Preprint <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17620502>
UDC 595.773.1(477.41)
urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:B1D557AA-EFEA-4463-A0DF-28036A09E201

A.V. Prokhorov*, **Yu.S. Vasilyeva**

I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology NAS of Ukraine,
Bogdana Khmelnytskoho, 15, Kyiv, 01054, Ukraine

* E-mail: al.val.prokhorov@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3367-260X>

THE HOVERFLIES (DIPTERA, SYRPHIDAE) OF KYIV REGION (UKRAINE)

A special study of the hoverflies in the Kyiv Region of Ukraine was carried out for the first time. References to the published literature, information on the examined actual material from 42 localities, and the flight period of the hoverflies in this region are provided. A total of 258 species were recorded in Kyiv Region, of which only five species are not supported by actual collected material.

Key words: *Ukraine, flower flies, annotated list.*

Introduction

In zoogeographical terms, the Kyiv Region occupies a very advantageous position in Eastern Europe. The northern part of the region lies in the Mixed Forest zone, while the southern part is occupied by the Wood-and-Steppe zone. The presence of the great Dnipro River implies a rich floodplain fauna. Some southern species may expand northwards along the river, which is also facilitated by climate warming. This explains the richness of the species composition of hoverflies in the Kyiv Region (more than half of all species found in Ukraine are present here).

No special studies of the hoverfly fauna were previously conducted in the Kyiv Region. Before 2015, when we started our survey, a few information on the distribution of some species in this region has been published (Kryshchal, 1949; Stackelberg, 1925, 1955, 1958, 1959, 1965; Violovitsh, 1960; Stackelberg & Richter, 1968; Zaika et al., 2011). In addition to our own collections,

Citation: Prokhorov A.V., Vasilyeva Yu.S. The Hoverflies (Diptera, Syrphidae) of Kyiv Region (Ukraine). *Ukrainian Entomological Journal*. 2024. Iss. 22. P. 152—185. (Preprint <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17620502>)

we have processed quite rich material collected mainly by M. Nesterov and M. Zaika between 2004 and 2018. Some contribution to the replenishment of the hoverfly collection of the Kyiv Region was also made by other colleagues (V. Ermolenko, V. Korneyev, G. Popov, V. Kavurka, A. Martynov, V. Nazarenko and B. Vasko).

The present paper provides a list of species based largely on published data in GBIF dataset (Prokhorov, 2023), as well as new collections and recently discovered old interesting finds.

Material and methods

All hoverfly specimens are deposited in the collection of the I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv.

Only material from the main collection included in the database is listed. Many specimens collected before 2015 have not yet been included in the main collection due to their poor condition. This material has only been used to provide a complete list of species and information on the phenology of species. Information on the material included in the main collection and collected before 2023 has mainly been published (Prokhorov, 2023). For this reason, we provide only brief information about previously published material: the number of males and females, the total number of sites from which they were collected, and in brackets the number of each site (see list below). In the list of sites we do not provide the coordinates of the collection points in such sites as Irpin, Kodra, Lisnyky, Mihalki and some others due to the number of different coordinates; they can be found in the publication (Prokhorov, 2023). We provide detailed labels for previously unpublished data from the main collection since 2023 (but only for peculiar and rare species). The ordinal number of the settlement (site) is also given in brackets after the name of the settlement.

The flight periods of the hoverflies are given only on the basis of actual collections and observations in the Kyiv Region: the earliest find – the latest one. The genera and species are listed in alphabetical order.

Sampling localities in Kyiv Region during the field work in 2005–2024:

1. **Antoniv:** 49.6215, 29.7887, orchard.
2. **Balyko-Shchuchynka env.,** 49.9624, 31.1191, ravine in deciduous forest.
3. **Dibrova env.,** 50.1944, 30.2036 (approximate data), no biotopical data available.
4. **Divychky env.,** 50.0441, 31.2730, sandy arena of the Dnipro River left bank.
5. **Fenevychi env.,** 50.8721, 30.0100, edge of mixed forest;
6. **Hrushiv env.,** 49.9, 31.2 (approximate data), no biotopical data available.
7. **Irpin env.,** investigated biotopes:
 - Irpin River floodplain meadow near mixed forest;
 - mixed forest (edges of the forest, roadsides, glades);
 - Lyubka River floodplain forest, wet glades;
8. **Ivankovychi env.,** 50.2692, 30.4684, Vita River valley, wet meadow.
9. **Kaharlyk,** 49.8650, 30.8096, in the garden.

Fig. 1. Map of the Kyiv Region with Syrphidae collection localities

Fig. 2. Map of the Kyiv city with Syrphidae collection localities

10. **Khodosivka**, Vita River valley, meadow hillsides, meadows and thickets of shrubs.
11. **Koblytsia env.**, 50.783, 29.919, deciduous forest.
12. **Kodra env.**, mixed forest (edges of the forest, roadsides, clearing, fellings).
13. **Kotsiubynske env.**, mixed forest (edges of the forest, roadsides, clearing, fellings);
14. **Kyiv: Batyieva Hora**, 50.4323, 30.4952 (approximate data), no biotopical data available.
15. **Kyiv: Dnipro River floodplain (Muromets Is. on Dnipro River)**, city park, floodplain forest and meadows.
16. **Kyiv: Dnipro River floodplain (Zhukiv Is. on Dnipro River)**, 50.33, 30.61 (approximate data), no biotopical data available.
17. **Kyiv: Lisove Lake**: 50.4650, 30.6741, the shore of a reservoir with flowering willows.
18. **Kyiv: Lysa Hora**, 50.3964, 30.5447 (approximate data), grassy slopes.
19. **Kyiv: Mykilskiy Lis**, 50.4080, 30.6979 (approximate data), mixed forest.
20. **Kyiv: Nyvky**, 50.4697, 30.4081, inside the house (on the balcony).
21. **Kyiv: Peremoha Park**, 50.4612, 30.6044 (approximate data), city park.
22. **Kyiv: Protasiv Yar**, 50.4224, 30.4946 (approximate data), wooded ravine in the city.
23. **Kyiv: Pyrohiv**, 50.3469, 30.5100 (approximate data), hillside meadow.
24. **Kyiv: Sviatoshinske Lake env.**, wasteland at the edge of mixed forest (50.464559, 30.324503) and roadsides (50.4544, 30.3382).
25. **Kyiv: Theophania Park and its environs**, city park, meadows, deciduous forest and wasteland.
26. **Kyiv: Trukhaniv Is. on Dnipro River**, 50.4596, 30.5402 (approximate data), no biotopical data available.
27. **Kyiv: Venetsianskiy Is. on Dnipro River (Hydropark)**, 50.44, 30.58 (approximate data), city park (floodplain forest, roadsides).
28. **Leonivka env.**, 50.7870, 29.9195, felling in mixed forest.
29. **Lisnyky env.**, investigated biotopes:
 - deciduous forest (edges of the forest, roadsides, glades, thickets along streams);
 - meadow at the edge of deciduous forest (near Shaparnia Lake);
 - mixed forest.
30. **Mali Dmytrovychi env.**, wooded ravine among agricultural fields (bottom of the ravine, meadow slopes, upper part of the ravine).
31. **Muzychi**, 50.3520, 30.1070 (approximate data), no biotopical data available.
32. **Myhalky env.**, investigated biotopes:
 - mixed forest (edges of the forest, roadsides, fellings, swampy glades with flowering *Salix* sp.);
 - edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*;
 - swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*;
 - Teteriv River floodplain forest (edges of the forest, glades, thickets and meadows along the channel);
 - edge of mixed forest and Teteriv River floodplain forest;

- swampy glades with thickets of shrubs at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest;
 - edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest;
 - Teteriv River floodplain meadow;
 - edge of mixed forest near Teteriv River floodplain;
 - meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel);
 - overgrown path with thickets of shrubs (along the channel) at the edges of floodplain meadow and floodplain forest;
 - edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and dry meadow on the sandy hill (along the channel);
 - dry meadow on the sandy hill at the edge of floodplain meadow;
 - mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel).
33. **Nova Buda env.**, investigated biotopes:
— mixed forest (edges of the forest, roadsides, clearing, fellings, glades);
— swampy mixed forest at the edge of the felling;
— swampy glades with flowering *Caltha palustris* in mixed forest;
34. **Olshanytsia env.**, 49.60, 30.60 (approximate data), felling in mixed forest.
35. **Piskivka env.**, investigated biotopes:
— 50.69, 29.6966, mixed forest;
— 50.6843, 29.6942, edge of mixed forest along railway;
— 50.690197, 29.691293, clearing in mixed forest.
36. **Potashnia env.**, Tal River floodplain forest.
37. **Rzhyshchiv**, investigated biotopes:
— 49.9750, 31.1052, deciduous forest;
— 49.9664, 31.1046, steppe ravine.
38. **Sobolivka env., Zalissia National Nature Park**: 50.729065, 30.815608, mixed forest near pond.
39. **Staiky env.**, 50.0514, 30.9335, in the garden.
40. **Ulianyky env.**, 49.9141, 31.1229, meadow along stream on the bottom of the ravine, edges of thickets of shrubs.
41. **Zakharivka env.**, 50.5969, 31.0036, deciduous forest.
42. **Zavorychi env.**, investigated biotopes:
— roadside (edge of the meadow along railway);
— deciduous forest (edge of the forest, roadsides, glades);
— meadow with thickets of shrubs at the edge of deciduous forest;

Results

To date, 258 species of hoverflies have been recorded from the Kyiv Region, of which *Chrysotoxum intermedium* Meigen, 1822, *C. lineare* (Zetterstedt, 1819), *Eristalis abusiva* Collin, 1931, *Meliscaeva cinctella* (Zetterstedt, 1843) and *Platycheirus clypeatus* Meigen, 1822 are not supported by actual collected material. The very uneven exploration of the region's territory gives us hope that new interesting discoveries await us in the future. Currently, among the species first recorded from Ukraine and not yet published, there are five species collected in the Kyiv Region, which are to be discussed in a separate article.

Annotated list of the hoverflies from Kyiv Region of Ukraine

Anasimyia contracta Claussen & Torp, 1980

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined: 1 ♂ from one locality (8).

Flight period: June 16.

Anasimyia interpuncta (Harris, 1776)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 6 ♀ from four localities (7, 29, 32, 33).

Flight period: April 17–June 05.

Baccha elongata (Fabricius, 1775)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 5 ♂, 5 ♀ from five localities (13, 29, 32, 33, 42).

Flight period: April 20–September 13.

Blera fallax (Linnaeus, 1758)

Stackelberg, 1958 (*Cynorrhina*); Prokhorov et al., 2018 d; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 14 ♂, 12 ♀ from three localities (12, 13, 32).

Flight period: May 01–June 20.

Brachyopa bicolor (Fallén, 1817)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 7 ♀ from four localities (3, 12, 32, 42).

New data: Myhalky env. (32): 50.6527, 29.4855, Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 01–02.05.2023, on trunks of *Quercus robur*, 5 ♂, 3 ♀; 50.6545, 29.4892, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 06.05.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: April 26–May 06.

Brachyopa dorsata Zetterstedt, 1837

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♀ from one locality (7).

Flight period: June 09.

Brachyopa insensilis Collin, 1939

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂ from two localities (13, 26).

Flight period: April 29–May 11.

Brachyopa maculipennis Thompson, 1980

Prokhorov et al., 2018 b.

Material examined. Kyiv (exact data not available), 09.06.2005, 1 ♂; Dibrova env. (3), 50.1944, 30.2036 (approximate data), 14.05.2006, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. (32), 50.6527, 29.4855, Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 01.05.2023, on trunk of *Quercus robur*, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: May 01–June 09.

Brachyopa pilosa Collin, 1939

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 29 ♂, 25 ♀ from six localities (7, 13, 29, 32, 35, 42).

Flight period: April 11–May 10.

Brachypalpoidea lentus (Meigen, 1822)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 2 ♀ from two localities (7, 13).

Flight period: May 21–June 05.

Brachypalpus laphriformis (Fallén, 1816)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 9 ♀ from four localities (7, 13, 15, 32).

Flight period: April 12–June 04.

Brachypalpus valgus (Panzer, 1798)

Stackelberg, 1965; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 13 ♂, 11 ♀ from six localities (7, 25, 29, 32, 35, 42).

Flight period: March 24–May 19.

Caliprobola speciosa (Rossi, 1790)

Prokhorov et al., 2018 d; Prokhorov & Shparyk, 2019; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 10 ♂, 1 ♀ from four localities (13, 15, 31, 32).

New data: Myhalky env. (32): 50.6531, 29.4907, Teteriv River floodplain forest, 28.05.2023, 1 ♂; 50.6544, 29.4908, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.06.2023, 1 ♂; 50.6547, 29.4900, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 04.06.2023, 1 ♂; 50.6549, 29.4952, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 06.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: May 06–June 04.

Callicera aenea (Fabricius, 1777)

Prokhorov et al., 2018 d; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 14 ♂ from two localities (7, 13).

Flight period: April 29–May 17.

Ceriana conopsoides (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 10 ♀ from five localities (7, 13, 25, 29, 32).

Flight period: May 07–August 03.

Chalcosyrphus (Xylotina) nemorum (Fabricius, 1805)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 9 ♀ from four localities (7, 29, 32, 33).

Flight period: April 10–September 17.

Chalcosyrphus (Xylotodes) eunotus (Loew, 1873)

Prokhorov et al., 2018 a; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 2 ♀ from three localities (7, 32, 36).

Flight period: April 11–May 22.

Chalcosyrphus (Xylotodes) piger (Fabricius, 1794)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 12 ♂, 8 ♀ from four localities (7, 12, 13, 32).

Flight period: April 28–August 31.

Chalcosyrphus (Xylotomima) femoratus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂ from two localities (7, 34).

Flight period: June 05.

***Chalcosyrphus (Xylotomima) valgus* (Gmelin, 1790)**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 4 ♀ from three localities (7, 29, 32).

Flight period: May 01–June 06.

***Cheilosia (Cheilosia) aerea* Dufour, 1848**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 15 ♂, 9 ♀ from five localities (7, 12, 13, 29, 32).

Flight period: April 20–July 23.

***Cheilosia (Cheilosia) albipila* Meigen, 1838**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 23 ♂, 9 ♀ from nine localities (3, 7, 10, 15, 17, 25, 29, 32, 42).

Flight period: March 19–April 28.

***Cheilosia (Cheilosia) albitarsis* (Meigen, 1822)**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂, 6 ♀ from four localities (7, 32, 33, 36).

Flight period: May 09–June 02.

***Cheilosia (Cheilosia) brunnipennis* Becker, 1894**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 5 ♀ from two localities (7, 32).

Flight period: April 11–30.

***Cheilosia (Cheilosia) carbonaria* Egger, 1860**

Material examined. Kyiv, Theophania Park (25) (exact data not available), 03.06.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Myhalky env. (32), 50.6531, 29.4849, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 19.07.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: June 03–July 19.

***Cheilosia (Cheilosia) chloris* (Meigen, 1822)**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 4 ♀ from two localities (25, 29).

Flight period: April 11–May 03.

***Cheilosia (Cheilosia) cynocephala* Loew, 1840**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 3 ♀ from three localities (7, 10, 38).

Flight period: April 17–August 17.

***Cheilosia (Cheilosia) flavipes* (Panzer, 1798)**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♀ from three localities (10, 26, 42).

New data: Kyiv, Trukhaniv Is. on Dnipro River (26) (exact data not available), 29.04.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Flight period: April 26–29.

***Cheilosia (Cheilosia) gigantea* (Zetterstedt, 1838)**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂ from one locality (13).

Flight period: May 13.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) grossa (Fallén, 1817)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 17 ♀ from seven localities (3, 7, 10, 13, 22, 32, 35).

Flight period: March 13–April 20.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) impressa Loew, 1840

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 5 ♀ from three localities (25, 29, 42).

Flight period: May 10–August 10.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) lasiopa Kowarz, 1885

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♀ from one locality (6).

Flight period: May 22.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) latifrons (Zetterstedt, 1843)

= *intonsa* Loew, 1857

Stackelberg, 1958: 225 (*intonsa*).

Material examined. Irpin env. (7) (exact data not available): 01.08.2004, 1 ♂ (M. Nesterov), 16.08.2013, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika); Kyiv (19), 50.4080, 30.6979 (approximate data), 15.05.2013, 2 ♂; Khodosivka (10) (exact data not available), 22.08.2013, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Flight period: May 15–August 22.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) mutabilis (Fallén, 1817)

Stackelberg, 1958; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 13 ♂, 10 ♀ from six localities (6, 7, 15, 25, 29, 30).

Flight period: May 19–July 31.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) nebulosa Verrall, 1871

Prokhorov et al., 2020 b; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 1 ♀ from one locality (32).

New data: Myhalky env. (32), 50.6546, 29.4892, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 14.05.2023, *Salix* sp. flowers, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: April 17–May 14.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) pagana (Meigen, 1822)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 3 ♀ from three localities (3, 7, 42).

Flight period: April 08–August 23.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) pascuorum Becker, 1894

Prokhorov et al., 2020 b; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 15 ♂, 2 ♀ from two localities (30, 32).

Flight period: April 23–May 08.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) proxima (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 15 ♂, 5 ♀ from five localities (7, 13, 25, 29, 42).

Flight period: April 11–August 23.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) psilophthalma Becker, 1894

Prokhorov et al., 2018 a; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 2 ♀ from two localities (7, 10).

Flight period: April 05–26.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) rufimana Becker, 1894

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 3 ♀ from three localities (7, 13, 15).

Flight period: April 06–May 13.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) urbana (Meigen, 1822)

= *ruralis* auct. nec (Meigen, 1822)

Stackelberg, 1958 (*ruralis*); Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 23 ♂, 24 ♀ from five localities (7, 13, 15, 29, 32).

Flight period: April 06–May 10.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) uviformis Becker, 1894

Prokhorov et al., 2020 b; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 1 ♀ from two localities (15, 32).

Flight period: April 06–May 10.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) variabilis (Panzer, 1798)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 10 ♂, 11 ♀ from six localities (7, 13, 29, 32, 36, 42).

Flight period: May 05–July 16.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) velutina Loew, 1840

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 1 ♀ from two localities (32, 42).

Flight period: July 16–August 24.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) vernalis (Fallén, 1817)

Stackelberg, 1958; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 10 ♂, 13 ♀ from eight localities (3, 6, 7, 10, 25, 29, 32, 42).

Flight period: April 05–September 26.

Cheilosia (Cheilosia) vulpina (Meigen, 1822)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 2 ♀ from two localities (6, 30).

Flight period: May 02–July 25.

Cheilosia (Eucartosyrphus) ruffipes (Preyssler, 1793)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 9 ♀ from one locality (29).

Flight period: July 23–September 04.

Cheilosia (Eucartosyrphus) scutellata (Fallén, 1817)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 5 ♂, 12 ♀ from six localities (7, 13, 15, 29, 30, 32).

Flight period: May 18–October 16.

Cheilosia (Floccocheila) illustrata (Harris, 1780)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 1 ♀ from two localities (7, 32).

Flight period: May 16–June 20.

Cheilosia (Pollinocheila) fasciata Schiner & Egger, 1853

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 9 ♂, 10 ♀ from one locality (29).

Flight period: April 10–28.

Cheilosia (Taeniochilosia) nigripes (Meigen, 1822)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 7 ♂, 8 ♀ from one locality (29).

Flight period: May 03–June 09.

Cheilosia (Taeniochilosia) pubera (Zetterstedt, 1838)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂, 10 ♀ from three localities (7, 29, 33).

Flight period: April 10–May 20.

Cheilosia (Taeniochilosia) vicina (Zetterstedt, 1849)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂ from three localities (7, 29, 42).

Flight period: April 25–May 03.

Chrysogaster cemiteriorum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 10 ♂, 9 ♀ from two localities (7, 32).

New data: Myhalky env. (32), 50.6526, 29.4835, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 17.07.2023, white Umbelliferae flowers, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: June 20–September 06.

Chrysogaster solstitialis (Fallén, 1817)

Stackelberg, 1958; Stackelberg, 1959; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂, 21 ♀ from four localities (2, 7, 12, 32).

Flight period: June 14–August 21.

Chrysotoxum bicinctum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♀ from one locality (30).

Flight period: July 05–August 08.

Chrysotoxum cautum (Harris, 1776)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 7 ♂, 9 ♀ from four localities (7, 15, 29, 32).

Flight period: May 03–June 08.

Chrysotoxum elegans Loew, 1841

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 12 ♀ from three localities (6, 10, 30).

Flight period: May 22–September 03.

Chrysotoxum intermedium Meigen, 1822

Kryshtal, 1949.

Material examined. Absent.

Flight period: no data.

Chrysotoxum lineare (Zetterstedt, 1819)

Kryshtal, 1949.

Material examined. Absent.

Flight period: no data.

Chrysotoxum festivum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 7 ♂, 3 ♀ from five localities (7, 10, 29, 30, 32).

Flight period: May 19–September 03.

***Chrysotoxum octomaculatum* Curtis, 1837**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 10 ♂, 4 ♀ from two localities (12, 32).

Flight period: May 08–August 14.

***Chrysotoxum vernale* Loew, 1841**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 7 ♂, 7 ♀ from five localities (12, 13, 29, 32, 36).

Flight period: April 27–June 07.

***Chrysotoxum verralli* (Collin, 1940)**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂, 8 ♀ from four localities (7, 12, 32, 42).

Flight period: June 05–August 31.

***Criorhina asilica* (Fallén, 1816)**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 9 ♂, 10 ♀ from three localities (13, 29, 32).

Flight period: May 03–28.

***Criorhina pachymera* Egger, 1858**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 7 ♂ from one locality (32).

New data: Myhalky env. (32), 50.6546, 29.4892, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 14–15.05.2023, *Acer tataricum* flowers, 6 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: May 14–22.

***Criorhina ranunculi* (Panzer, 1803)**

Stackelberg, 1955 (*Penthesilea*); 1958 (*Penthesilea*); Stackelberg & Richter, 1968; Prokhorov et al., 2018 d; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 13 ♂, 14 ♀ from eight localities (7, 10, 12, 13, 15, 29, 32, 42).

Flight period: March 19–May 17.

***Dasysyrphus albostriatus* (Fallén, 1817)**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 5 ♂, 5 ♀ from five localities (7, 13, 29, 32, 42).

Flight period: May 03–July 23.

***Dasysyrphus hilaris* (Zetterstedt, 1843)**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♀ from two localities (32, 36).

Flight period: May 06–June 14.

***Dasysyrphus neovenustus* Soszyński, Mielczarek & Tofilski, 2013**

Prokhorov et al., 2023; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 26 ♂, 14 ♀ from six localities (3, 7, 13, 32, 33, 36).

Flight period: April 12–May 21.

***Dasysyrphus pauxillus* (Williston, 1887)**

Prokhorov et al., 2020 b; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 5 ♂, 6 ♀ from four localities (3, 7, 32, 33).

Flight period: April 12–May 14.

Dasysyrphus tricinctus (Fallén, 1817)

Violovitsh, 1960 (*Syrphus*); Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 6 ♀ from four localities (13, 29, 32, 36).

Flight period: April 17–August 31.

Dasysyrphus venustus (Meigen, 1822)

Stackelberg, 1958 (*Syrphus*); Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 18 ♂, 13 ♀ from seven localities (7, 12, 13, 29, 32, 33, 35).

Flight period: April 14–May 21.

***Dasysyrphus* sp.**

Material examined. Myhalky env. (32): 50.6525, 29.4880, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 13–15.05.2020, 2 ♀; 50.6549, 29.4952, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 06.06.2020, 1 ♀, 01.05.2024, 2 ♂; 50.6546, 29.4892, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 11.05.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: May 01–June 06.

Remarks. All caught specimens have a clear set of features that do not allow them to be classified as either *Dasysyrphus hilaris* (Zetterstedt, 1843) or *D. venustus* (Meigen, 1822).

Didea alneti (Fallén, 1817)

Stackelberg, 1958; Violovitsh, 1960; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 11 ♀ from four localities (10, 12, 13, 32).

Flight period: April 23–August 23.

Didea fasciata Macquart, 1834

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 7 ♂, 5 ♀ from three localities (7, 25, 32).

Flight period: May 01–October 16.

Didea intermedia Loew, 1854

Stackelberg, 1958; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 12 ♀ from seven localities (7, 13, 24, 29, 30, 32, 39).

Flight period: May 08–September 28.

Doros profuges (Harris, 1779)

Prokhorov et al., 2017 b; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂ from two localities (7, 34).

Flight period: June 02–11.

Epistrophe eligans (Harris, 1780)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 7 ♀ from seven localities (7, 13, 25, 29, 32, 36, 42).

Flight period: April 11–May 11.

Epistrophe flava Doczkal & Schmid, 1994

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 4 ♀ from three localities (13, 29, 34).

Flight period: May 11–June 09.

Epistrophe grossulariae (Meigen, 1822)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♀ from three localities (22, 32, 36).

Flight period: June 24–August 08.

Epistrophe melanostoma (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 11 ♂, 16 ♀ from five localities (7, 13, 15, 29, 32).

Flight period: April 06–May 13.

Epistrophe nitidicollis (Megerle in Meigen, 1822)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 17 ♂, 18 ♀ from eight localities (7, 12, 13, 25, 29, 32, 33, 36).

Flight period: April 14–June 03.

Epistrophe ochrostoma (Zetterstedt, 1849)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 1 ♀ from four localities (15, 27, 29, 32).

Flight period: April 06–28.

Epistrophe olgae Mutin, 1990

Prokhorov et al., 2018 c; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 18 ♂, 10 ♀ from four localities (7, 13, 32, 36).

Flight period: April 12–May 13.

Epistrophella euchroma (Kowarz, 1885)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 14 ♂, 17 ♀ from seven localities (7, 13, 15, 29, 30, 32, 35).

Flight period: April 06–May 13.

Episyrphus balteatus (De Geer, 1776)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 10 ♂, 12 ♀ from eight localities (3, 7, 13, 25, 29, 30, 32, 36).

Flight period: March 19–December 21.

Eristalinus (Eristalinus) sepulchralis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 4 ♀ from four localities (9, 13, 29, 32).

Flight period: May 11–August 24.

Eristalinus (Lathyrophthalmus) aeneus (Scopoli, 1763)

Kryshtal, 1949 (*Lathyrophthalmus*); Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 7 ♀ from five localities (7, 10, 25, 29, 39).

Flight period: March 29–October 08.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) abusiva Collin, 1931

Kryshtal, 1949.

Material examined. Absent.

Flight period: no data.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) arbustorum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 5 ♂, 10 ♀ from seven localities (7, 9, 15, 29, 30, 32, 40).

Flight period: April 13–October 16.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) horticola (De Geer, 1776)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 5 ♂, 4 ♀ from three localities (7, 13, 32).

Flight period: May 11–August 19.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) intricaria (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 18 ♂, 16 ♀ from seven localities (7, 12, 13, 29, 30, 32, 37).

Flight period: April 23–August 29.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) nemorum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Kryshtal, 1949; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂, 4 ♀ from three localities (7, 29, 32).

Flight period: April 28–August 29.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) obscura Loew, 1866

= *vitripennis* auct. nec Strobl, 1893

Stackelberg, 1958 (*Eristalis (Eristalis) vitripennis*); Prokhorov & Popov, 2017; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 16 ♀ from five localities (7, 12, 13, 29, 32).

Flight period: May 11–August 31.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) oestracea (Linnaeus, 1758)

Stackelberg, 1958 (ssp. *Eristalomyia*); Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 11 ♀ from three localities (4, 7, 32).

Flight period: May 14–August 19.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) pertinax (Scopoli, 1763)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 12 ♀ from six localities (7, 10, 29, 30, 32, 42).

Flight period: April 05–October 29.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) picea (Fallén, 1817)

Prokhorov & Popov, 2017; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 13 ♂, 12 ♀ from five localities (7, 13, 29, 32, 33).

Flight period: April 12–June 03.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) rupium Fabricius, 1805

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♀ from one locality (32).

Flight period: May 14.

Remarks. The only specimen caught was a small female with inconspicuous features, but the shiny posterior edge of the tergites clearly identifies it as this species.

Eristalis (Eoseristalis) similis (Fallén, 1817)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 7 ♀ from five localities (7, 10, 29, 30, 32).

Flight period: April 05–July 22.

Eristalis (Eristalis) tenax (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 5 ♂, 6 ♀ from six localities (13, 30, 32, 33, 37, 42).

Flight period: March 19–November 14.

Remarks. One of the most common species throughout Ukraine.

Eumerus amoenus Loew, 1848

Material examined. Staiiky env. (39), 50.051409, 30.933455, in the garden, at the edge of mixed forest, 27–28.09.2023, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: September 27–28.

Remarks. The finding of the species in the Kyiv Region is the first discovery on mainland Ukraine.

Eumerus flavitarsis Zetterstedt, 1843

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 1 ♀ from three localities (29, 32, 34).

Flight period: June 06–August 23.

Eumerus funeralis Megerle in Meigen, 1822

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♀ from three localities (3, 32, 39).

Flight period: May 03–September 28.

Eumerus ornatus Meigen, 1822

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂ from one locality (25).

Flight period: June 06–15.

Eumerus ovatus Loew, 1848

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 2 ♀ from four localities (3, 4, 7, 34).

Flight period: May 21–August 06.

Eumerus sogdianus Stackelberg, 1952

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♀ from one locality (10).

Flight period: August 17.

Eumerus strigatus (Fallén, 1817)

Material examined. Khodosivka (10) (exact data not available), 06.06.2014, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika).

Flight period: June 06.

Eumerus tricolor (Fabricius, 1798)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂ from two localities (6, 23).

Flight period: May 21–June 20.

Eupeodes bucculatus (Rondani, 1857)

Prokhorov et al., 2017 b (*nuba*: misidentification); Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂, 1 ♀ from three localities (25, 32, 35).

Flight period: April 11–August 23.

Eupeodes corollae (Fabricius, 1794)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 13 ♀ from four localities (7, 25, 29, 32).

Flight period: April 07–November 09.

Eupeodes latifasciatus (Macquart, 1829)

Kryshstal, 1949 (*Syrphus*); Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 13 ♀ from four localities (12, 15, 29, 32).

Flight period: April 09–September 21.

Eupeodes lundbecki (Soot-Ryen, 1946)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 5 ♀ from three localities (3, 13, 32).

Flight period: April 25–September 09.

Eupeodes luniger (Meigen, 1822)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 15 ♂, 15 ♀ from seven localities (3, 7, 12, 15, 29, 30, 32).

Flight period: April 12–November 13.

Eupeodes nitens (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Stackelberg, 1958 (*Syrphus*); Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♀ from one locality (32).

Flight period: April 28.

Eurimyia lineata (Fabricius, 1787)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 3 ♀ from two localities (32, 33).

Flight period: May 08–July 19.

Fagisyrphus cinctus (Fallén, 1817)

Kryshthal, 1949 (*Syrphus*); Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 12 ♂, 6 ♀ from five localities (13, 25, 29, 32, 33).

Flight period: April 14–July 29.

Ferdinandea cuprea (Scopoli, 1763)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 16 ♂, 18 ♀ from eight localities (7, 12, 13, 25, 29, 32, 41, 42).

Flight period: April 25–September 23.

Ferdinandea ruficornis (Fabricius, 1775)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 7 ♀ from five localities (3, 7, 12, 36, 42).

New data: Kodra env. (11), 50.6323, 29.4828, felling in mixed forest, 28.04.2024, on *Quercus robur* trunk, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: April 28–July 19.

Helophilus continuus Loew, 1854

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 1 ♀ from two localities (7, 10).

New data: Irpin env. (7) (exact data not available), 09.10.2014, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika).

Flight period: October 09–13.

Helophilus hybridus Loew, 1846

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 4 ♀ from three localities (7, 29, 32).

Flight period: May 03–August 19.

Helophilus pendulus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 7 ♂, 7 ♀ from six localities (7, 13, 25, 29, 32, 33).

Flight period: April 17–September 17.

Helophilus trivittatus (Fabricius, 1805)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 5 ♀ from six localities (2, 7, 13, 15, 32, 33).

Flight period: May 09–October 23.

Heringia heringi (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 11 ♂, 9 ♀ from five localities (12, 13, 25, 29, 32).

Flight period: April 25–June 12.

Lapposyrphus lapponicus (Zetterstedt, 1838)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂, 4 ♀ from six localities (7, 17, 25, 29, 32, 34).

Flight period: March 31–June 11.

Lejogaster metallina (Fabricius, 1777)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 2 ♀ from one locality (3).

Flight period: May 28–July 24.

Lejogaster tarsata (Megerle in Meigen, 1822)

Material examined. Kyiv, Pyrohiv (23) (exact data not available), 21.06.2005, hillside, 1 ♀ (M. Nesterov); Dibrova env. (3), 50.1944, 30.2036 (approximate data), 30.06.2006, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Flight period: June 21–30.

Lejota ruficornis (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂ from two localities (7, 29).

Flight period: April 26–May 25.

Mallota fuciformis (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined. Antoniv (1), 49.6214, 29.7887, orchard, 30.04.2022, 2 ♀ at the walnut hollow, 1 ♀ at the apple tree hollow; 3.06.2022, 2 ♀ (visual observation); 5.05.2022, 2 ♀; 6.05.2022, 1 ♀; 9.05.2022, 1 ♀ (visual observation); 17.05.2022, 1 ♀ (visual observation) (G. Popov).

Flight period: April 30–May 17.

Remarks. In Ukraine, the species was previously known only from the Carpathians.

Mallota megilliformis (Fallén, 1817)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 7 ♂, 1 ♀ from one locality (32).

Flight period: May 18–June 15.

Mallota tricolor Loew, 1871

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 5 ♂, 5 ♀ from five localities (7, 16, 20, 25, 32).

New data: Myhalky env. (30): 50.6544, 29.4908, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 04.06.2023, 1 ♀; 50.6549, 29.4952, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 19.05.2024, 2 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: May 19–June 29.

Matsumyia berberina (Fabricius, 1805)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 6 ♀ from two localities (32, 36).

Flight period: May 08–June 24.

Megasyrphus erraticus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♀ from one locality (32).

Flight period: May 13.

Melangyna lasiophthalma (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 13 ♂, 24 ♀ from six localities (3, 7, 13, 15, 24, 32).

Flight period: March 19–May 04.

Melangyna lucifera Nielsen, 1980

Prokhorov et al., 2017 a; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂, 19 ♀ from seven localities (3, 7, 13, 15, 22, 29, 32).

Flight period: March 19–April 22.

Melangyna quadrimaculata (Verrall, 1873)

Prokhorov et al., 2020 b; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♀ from one locality (25).

Flight period: March 28.

Melangyna umbellatarum (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined. Dibrova env. (3), 50.1944, 30.2036 (approximate data), 08.08.2006, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Flight period: August 08.

Melanogaster aerosa (Loew, 1843)

= *macquarti* auctt., nec Loew, 1843.

Stackelberg, 1958 (*Chrysogaster macquarti*); Stackelberg & Richter, 1968 (*Chrysogaster macquarti*); Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 2 ♀ from two localities (7, 32).

Flight period: May 11–June 12.

Melanogaster nuda (Macquart, 1829)

= *viduata* auctt., nec Linnaeus, 1758.

Stackelberg, 1958 (*Chrysogaster viduata*); Stackelberg, 1959 (*Chrysogaster viduata*); Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 5 ♀ from four localities (6, 7, 13, 25).

Flight period: May 19–June 01.

Melanogaster parumplicata (Loew, 1840)

Prokhorov et al., 2020 a; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♀ from one locality (7).

Flight period: May 05–June 02.

Melanostoma mellinum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Kryshtal, 1949; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 12 ♂, 10 ♀ from eight localities (2, 7, 10, 12, 13, 28, 29, 32).

Flight period: April 22–October 29.

Melanostoma scalare (Fabricius, 1794)

Kryshtal, 1949; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 8 ♀ from five localities (7, 29, 30, 32, 36).

Flight period: April 25–September 03.

Meligramma triangulifera (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 15 ♂, 20 ♀ from six localities (7, 13, 15, 29, 32, 35).

Flight period: April 10–August 09.

Meliscaeva auricollis (Meigen, 1822)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂, 5 ♀ from four localities (7, 15, 29, 32).

Flight period: April 08–June 06.

Meliscaeva cinctella (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Violovitsh, 1960 (*Syrphus*).

Material examined. Absent.

Flight period: no data.

Merodon aberrans Egger, 1860

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂ from one locality (18).

Flight period: July 04.

Merodon equestris (Fabricius, 1794)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂ from three localities (13, 14, 21).

Flight period: May 13–30.

Merodon moenium Wiedemann in Meigen, 1822

Prokhorov et al., 2018 b; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂ from one locality (30).

Flight period: July 05–13.

Merodon ruficornis Meigen, 1822

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂, 3 ♀ from two localities (29, 37).

Flight period: April 28–May 21.

Merodon rufus Meigen, 1838

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂ from two localities (7, 34).

Flight period: June 02–11.

Mesembrius peregrinus (Loew, 1846)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 5 ♀ from three localities (7, 29, 32).

Flight period: May 24–August 03.

Microdon analis (Macquart, 1842)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 2 ♀ from four localities (22, 25, 26, 29).

Flight period: May 03–June 01.

Microdon devius (Linnaeus, 1761)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 1 ♀ from three localities (25, 29, 30).

Flight period: June 01–July 05.

Microdon mutabilis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Kyiv, Pyrohiv (23) (exact data not available), 20.05.2013, 1 ♂; Kyiv, Theophania Park (25) (exact data not available), 21.05.2013, 1 ♀; Hrushiv env. (6) (exact data not available), 21.05.2018, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Flight period: May 20–21.

Remarks. The studied specimens of the species are clearly distinguished by their large size and darker tarsi from a series of specimens of the smaller cryptic species *M. myrmicae* Schönrogge, Barr, Wardlaw, Napper, Gardner, Breen, Elmes & Thomas, 2002, caught in the Rivne Region.

Myathropa florea (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 7 ♂, 10 ♀ from seven localities (2, 7, 12, 13, 29, 32, 42).

Flight period: April 28–October 16.

Myolepta dubia (Fabricius, 1805)

Material examined. Kyiv, Protasiv Yar (22), 50.4224, 30.4946 (approximate data), 17.06.2010, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Flight period: June 17.

Myolepta vara (Panzer, 1798)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♀ from one locality (13).

Flight period: May 13–17.

Neoascia (Neoascia) podagrica (Fabricius, 1775)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♀ from three localities (7, 32, 40).

New data: Myhalky env. (32), 50.6538, 29.4863, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and dry meadow on the sandy hill (along the channel), 02.09.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: July 27–October 10.

Neoascia (Neoascia) tenur (Harris, 1780)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 18 ♀ from six localities (3, 7, 10, 29, 32, 33).

Flight period: April 18–August 17.

Neoascia (Neosciella) interrupta (Megerle in Meigen, 1822)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 16 ♀ from three localities (29, 32, 33).

Flight period: April 17–September 13.

Neoascia (Neosciella) meticulosa (Scopoli, 1763)

= *aenea* (Meigen, 1822)

Stackelberg, 1958 (*aenea*); Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 7 ♂, 15 ♀ from four localities (7, 29, 32, 33).

Flight period: April 09–June 02.

Neocnemodon brevidens (Egger, 1865)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 3 ♀ from three localities (15, 25, 32).

Flight period: May 01–July 27.

Neocnemodon latitarsis (Egger, 1865)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 5 ♀ from three localities (7, 12, 32).

New data: Kodra env. (12), 50.6306, 29.4871, mixed forest, roadside, 14.07.2023, *Quercus rubra* leaves (with honey dew), 1 ♂; Mygalky env. (32), 50.6517, 29.4886, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 20.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: April 20–July 27.

Neocnemodon verrucula (Collin, 1931)

Prokhorov et al., 2023; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 7 ♀ from two localities (32, 33).

Flight period: April 21–May 05.

Neocnemodon vitripennis (Meigen, 1822)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 3 ♀ from four localities (12, 19, 32, 33).

New data: Kyiv, Mykil'skiy Lis (19), 50.4080, 30.6979 (approximate data), mixed forest, 08.05.2014, 2 ♂ (M. Zaika); Kodra env. (12), 50.6306, 29.4871, mixed forest, roadside, 10–14.07.2023, *Quercus rubra* leaves (with honey dew), 2 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: April 28–July 14.

Orthonevra brevicornis (Loew, 1843)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 14 ♂, 20 ♀ from two localities (32, 33).

Flight period: April 19–May 22.

Orthonevra elegans (Wiedemann in Meigen, 1822)

Violovitsh, 1960; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 2 ♀ from two localities (7, 32).

Flight period: June 12–July 23.

Orthonevra geniculata (Meigen, 1830)

Prokhorov et al., 2018 b; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 10 ♂, 31 ♀ from four localities (3, 7, 32, 33).

Flight period: April 12–May 16.

Orthonevra incisa (Loew, 1843)

Prokhorov et al., 2023; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 2 ♀ from one locality (33).

Flight period: April 23–May 05.

Orthonevra intermedia Lundbeck, 1916

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 12 ♂, 7 ♀ from two localities (7, 32).

Flight period: May 29–July 28.

Orthonevra nobilis (Fallén, 1817)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 2 ♀ from one locality (3).

Flight period: July 07–August 04.

Paragus (Pandasyopthalmus) constrictus Šimić, 1986

Material examined. Kodra env. (12): 50.6323, 29.4828, felling in mixed forest, 27–28.04.2024, 2 ♂, 1 ♀; 50.6333, 29.4817, roadside along felling in mixed forest, 28.04.2024, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ in copula (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: April 27–28.

Paragus (Pandasyopthalmus) haemorrhous Megerle in Meigen, 1822

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 9 ♂, 3 ♀ from seven localities (7, 12, 18, 29, 30, 32, 39).

Flight period: April 28–October 18.

Paragus (Paragus) albifrons (Fallén, 1817)

Kryshtal, 1949; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♂ from one locality (12).

Flight period: July 01.

Paragus (Paragus) finitimus Goeldlin de Tiefenau, 1971

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂ from one locality (30).

Flight period: July 25–August 11.

Paragus (Paragus) aff. flammeus Goeldlin de Tiefenau, 1971

Material examined. Kotsiubynske env. (13), 50.4709, 30.2873, edge of mixed forest, 14.05.2021, 1 ♂; Kodra env. (12): 50.6333, 29.4817, roadside along felling in mixed forest, 28.04.2024, 4 ♂, 3 ♀; 3.05.2024, 2 ♂; 50.6352, 29.4774, felling in mixed forest, 17.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: April 28–August 17.

Remarks. The available material requires more thorough study, especially of the structures of the male genitalia.

Paragus (Paragus) hyalopteri Marcos-García & Rojo, 1994

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♂ from one locality (32).

Flight period: June 10.

Remarks. The finding of the species in the Kyiv Region is the first discovery in mainland Ukraine.

Paragus (Paragus) pecchiolii Rondani, 1857

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 22 ♂, 16 ♀ from six localities (7, 13, 29, 32, 33, 36).

Flight period: April 28–September 06.

Paragus (Paragus) quadrifasciatus Meigen, 1822

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 1 ♀ from four localities (6, 10, 18, 32).

Flight period: April 28–September 11.

Parasyrphus nigratarsis (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 2 ♀ from one locality (32).

New data: Myhalky env. (32), 50.6513, 29.4885, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 22.04.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: April 22–May 10.

Parasyrphus punctulatus (Verrall, 1873)

Material examined. Myhalky env. (32), 50.6549, 29.4952, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 12.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: April 12.

Remarks. The first and only specimen of this species from the Kyiv Region.

Parhelophilus frutetorum (Fabricius, 1775)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 7 ♂, 12 ♀ from five localities (7, 13, 25, 32, 33).

Flight period: May 11–July 23.

Parhelophilus versicolor (Fabricius, 1794)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 6 ♀ from five localities (7, 13, 29, 32, 42).

Flight period: May 03–July 16.

Pipiza accola Virolvitsh, 1985

Prokhorov et al., 2018 c; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 18 ♂, 15 ♀ from three localities (7, 13, 32).

Flight period: April 11–May 13.

Pipiza fasciata Meigen, 1822

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 14 ♀ from four localities (7, 13, 29, 32).

Flight period: April 27–May 20.

Pipiza festiva Meigen, 1822

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 2 ♀ from three localities (3, 9, 22).

Flight period: August 02–September 28.

Pipiza lugubris (Fabricius, 1775)

Material examined. Dibrova env. (3), 50.1944, 30.2036 (approximate data), 04.08.2006, 1 ♂; Khodosivka (10) (exact data not available), 24.07.2014, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Flight period: July 24–August 04.

Pipiza luteitarsis Zetterstedt, 1843

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 3 ♀ from two localities (32, 35).

Flight period: April 23–May 09.

Pipiza noctiluca (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 11 ♂, 11 ♀ from four localities (7, 13, 25, 32).

Flight period: April 10–August 03.

Pipiza notata Meigen, 1822

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 1 ♀ from three localities (6, 29, 32).

Flight period: April 28–July 27.

Pipizella annulata (Macquart, 1829)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 3 ♀ from one locality (7).

Flight period: June 01–30.

Pipizella viduata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 10 ♂ from five localities (10, 13, 29, 30, 32).

Flight period: May 03–August 17.

Pipizella virens (Fabricius, 1805)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂ from two localities (6, 25).

Flight period: May 31–June 01.

Platycheirus albimanus (Fabricius, 1781)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 3 ♀ from four localities (7, 13, 29, 32).

New data: Myhalky env. (32), 50.6513, 29.4885, swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 25.04.2023, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: April 25–May 17.

Platycheirus ambiguus (Fallén, 1817)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 1 ♀ from two localities (30, 32).

Flight period: April 23–May 01.

Platycheirus angustatus (Zetterstedt, 1843)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 12 ♂, 9 ♀ from two localities (7, 32).

Flight period: April 18–August 25.

Platycheirus clypeatus (Meigen, 1822)

Kryshtal, 1949.

Material examined. Absent.

Flight period: no data.

Platycheirus europaeus Goeldlin de Tiefenau, Maibach & Speight, 1990

Prokhorov et al., 2023; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 1 ♀ from one locality (33).

Flight period: May 16.

Platycheirus fulviventris (Macquart, 1829)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 15 ♂, 22 ♀ from four localities (7, 10, 32, 33).

Flight period: April 13–September 08.

Platycheirus occultus Goeldlin de Tiefenau, Maibach & Speight, 1990

Prokhorov et al., 2018 c; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 28 ♂, 28 ♀ from six localities (7, 12, 15, 30, 32, 33).

Flight period: April 09–August 23.

Platycheirus peltatus (Meigen, 1822)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂ from one locality (7).

Flight period: May 21.

Platycheirus scutatus (Meigen, 1822)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 19 ♀ from six localities (7, 13, 19, 25, 29, 32).

Flight period: May 01–September 18.

Platycheirus sticticus (Meigen, 1822)

Prokhorov et al., 2023; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♀ from one locality (7).

Flight period: July 23.

Remarks. The only studied specimen of this species not only for the Kyiv Region, but for the whole of Ukraine.

***Platycheirus* aff. *brunnifrons* Nielsen, 2004**

Material examined. Myhalky env. (32): 50.6568, 29.4975, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 16.04.2017, 2 ♀, 21.04.2018, 2 ♀; 50.6566, 29.4970, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 22.04.2021, 2 ♂, 1 ♀; 50.6564, 29.4968, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 9.04.2020, 2 ♂, 4 ♀, 28.04.2021, 2 ♀; 50.6551, 29.4945, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 18–24.04.2020, 3 ♀, 28.04.2021, 1 ♂, 2 ♀, 28.04.2022, 1 ♀; 50.6555, 29.4953, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 29.04.2021, 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: April 09–29.

Remarks. The species was found only in a few very small meadow habitats in the Teteriv River floodplain. It is possibly a new species to science. Males are most closely related to *Platycheirus brunnifrons* Nielsen, 2004, while females are not identified at all by available identification keys (Nielsen, 2004, 2014). Preferred environment and flight period of this species are completely different from those given in Syrph the Net for *P. brunnifrons* (Speight, 2020).

***Platycheirus* aff. *goeldini* Nielsen, 2004**

Material examined. Myhalky env. (32), 50.6568, 29.4975, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (near channel), 28.04.2021, *Salix* sp. flowers, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: April 28.

Remarks. Quite easily identified by the identification keys (Nielsen, 2004, 2014). However, the preferred habitats and flight periods are completely different from those indicated in Syrph the Net for *P. goeldini* (Speight, 2020).

***Pocota personata* (Harris, 1780)**

Prokhorov et al., 2018 a; Prokhorov & Shparyk, 2019; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 3 ♀ from three localities (7, 13, 32).

New data: Myhalky env. (32): 50.6517, 29.4886, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 14.05.2023, 1 ♀; 50.6546, 29.4892, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 15.05.2023, *Acer tataricum* flowers, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: May 05–June 08.

***Psarus abdominalis* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Zaika et al., 2011; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 12 ♂, 7 ♀ from four localities (7, 12, 13, 32).

New data: Myhalky env. (32): 50.6549, 29.4952, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 20.05.2023, *Acer tataricum* flowers, 1 ♀; 50.6531, 29.4849, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 19.07.2023, 1 ♀; Kodra env. (12), 50.6323, 29.4828, felling in mixed forest, 27.04.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: April 27–July 27.

***Psilota atra* (Fallén, 1817)**

Prokhorov et al., 2018 b; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 10 ♀ from three localities (13, 25, 32).

New data: Myhalky env. (32), 50.6546, 29.4892, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 14–15.05.2023, *Acer tataricum* and *Salix* sp. flowers, 5 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: April 25–May 18.

***Psilota innupta* Rondani, 1857**

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 17 ♂, 22 ♀ from three localities (7, 13, 32).

Flight period: April 13–May 15.

***Pyrophaena granditarsa* (Forster, 1771)**

Material examined. Myhalky env. (32), 50.6559, 29.4941, Teteriv River floodplain meadow (near channel), 15.06.2023, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: June 15.

Remarks. The first and only specimen of this species from the Kyiv Region.

Pyrophaena rosarum (Fabricius, 1787)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂ from two localities (7, 32).

Flight period: May 04–September 02.

Rhingia campestris Meigen, 1822

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 5 ♂, 8 ♀ from two localities (29, 36).

Flight period: April 28–July 19.

Rhingia rostrata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined. Kyiv: Protasiv Yar (22), 50.4224, 30.4946 (approximate data), 23.06.2007, 2 ♀; Batyieva Hora (14) (exact data not available), 23.09.2007, 1 ♀ (M. Zaika).

Flight period: June 23–September 23.

Scaeva dignota (Rondani, 1857)

Material examined. Dibrova env. (3), 50.1944, 30.2036 (approximate data), 01.07.2006, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika).

Flight period: July 01.

Remarks. The first and only specimen of this species from the Kyiv Region.

Scaeva pyrastris (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 7 ♂, 4 ♀ from four localities (12, 29, 32, 39).

Flight period: May 30–October 21.

Scaeva selenitica (Meigen, 1822)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 10 ♀ from six localities (7, 12, 15, 22, 25, 32).

Flight period: March 29–July 05.

Sericomyia (Sericomyia) silentis (Harris, 1778)

Stackelberg, 1958 (*Cinxia*); Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 2 ♀ from one locality (32).

New data: Myhalky env. (32): 50.6487, 29.4888, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 11.05.2024, *Acer tataricum* flowers, 1 ♂; 50.6527, 29.4842, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (bank of the channel), 31.08.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: May 11–September 10.

Sphaerophoria chongjini Bańkowska, 1964

Material examined. Myhalky env. (32), 50.6541, 29.4870, meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, overgrown path with thickets of shrubs (along the channel), 04.07.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: July 04.

Remarks. The only studied specimen of this species from the Kyiv Region.

Sphaerophoria rueppelli (Wiedemann, 1830)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂ from one locality (10).

Flight period: May 13–August 17.

Sphaerophoria scripta (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 2 ♀ from one locality (12, 33).

Flight period: April 14–October 16.

Remarks. This amount of studied material does not correspond to the actual abundance of the species. This is one of the most common species, it was simply not considered necessary to collecting it.

Sphaerophoria taeniata (Meigen, 1822)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♂ from one locality (32).

Flight period: June 18.

Remarks. One of the most common *Sphaerophoria* species in Ukraine, but the only studied specimen of this species from the Kyiv Region.

Sphaerophoria virgata Goeldlin de Tiefenau, 1974

Material examined. Kotsiubynske env. (13), 50.4730, 30.2897, edge of mixed forest, 01.06.2021, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: June 01.

Remarks. The only studied specimen of this species from the Kyiv Region.

Sphegina (Sphegina) clavata (Scopoli, 1763)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 1 ♀ from two localities (7, 32).

Flight period: May 12–June 30.

Sphegina (Sphegina) elegans Schummel, 1843

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 12 ♂, 17 ♀ from four localities (2, 3, 7, 32).

Flight period: June 04–August 05.

Sphiximorpha garibaldii Rondani, 1860

Prokhorov et al., 2020 a; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♀ from one locality (7).

Flight period: June 26.

Remarks. The only studied specimen of this species from the Kyiv Region.

Sphiximorpha subsessilis (Illiger in Rossi, 1807)

Prokhorov et al., 2018 d; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 1 ♀ from three localities (3, 7, 15).

New data: Dibrova env. (3), 50.1944, 30.2036 (approximate data), 08.05.2010, 1 ♂ (M. Zaika).

Flight period: May 08–June 01.

Spilomyia diophthalma (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 13 ♂, 12 ♀ from five localities (7, 12, 29, 32, 33).

Flight period: July 05–August 31.

Spilomyia manicata (Rondani, 1865)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 7 ♂, 7 ♀ from four localities (7, 29, 30, 32).

Flight period: July 23–August 31.

Spilomyia saltuum (Fabricius, 1794)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 3 ♀ from four localities (7, 12, 30, 32).

New data: Kodra env. (12), 50.6336, 29.4804, felling in mixed forest, 25.07.2023, white Umbelliferae flowers, 1 ♂, 1 ♀; Myhalky env. (32), 50.6526, 29.4835, mixed grass meadow at the edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 31.08.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: July 23–August 31.

Remarks. Until 2020, this rare species had not been recorded in the Kyiv Region. However, after that year, *S. saltuum* clearly increased its numbers.

Syritta pipiens (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 12 ♀ from six localities (7, 10, 13, 29, 30, 32).

Flight period: April 08–August 31.

Syrphus ribesii (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 12 ♂, 7 ♀ from seven localities (7, 13, 15, 29, 32, 35, 42).

Flight period: April 10–October 15.

Syrphus torvus Osten Sacken, 1875

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 9 ♂, 8 ♀ from six localities (7, 13, 15, 29, 32, 35).

Flight period: April 09–October 29.

Syrphus vitripennis Megerle in Meigen, 1822

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 5 ♀ from seven localities (2, 7, 13, 29, 32, 35, 36).

Flight period: April 23–October 16.

Temnostoma bombylans (Fabricius, 1805)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 9 ♀ from seven localities (7, 13, 22, 25, 32, 36, 38).

Flight period: May 01–June 22.

Temnostoma meridionale Krivosheina & Mamayev, 1962

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 9 ♀ from three localities (29, 32, 36).

Flight period: May 03–June 08.

Temnostoma vespiforme (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 6 ♀ from four localities (7, 25, 32, 36).

Flight period: May 01–June 30.

Trichopsomyia flavitarsis (Meigen, 1822)

Kryshtal, 1949 (*Pipizella*).

Material examined. Kodra env. (12), 50.6306, 29.4870, mixed forest, roadside, 21.06.2024, *Quercus rubra* leaves (with honey dew), 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: June 21.

Remarks. The only studied specimen of this species from the Kyiv Region.

Triglyphus primus Loew, 1840

Stackelberg, 1958; Violovitsh, 1960; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 5 ♂, 1 ♀ from four localities (3, 7, 13, 33).

Flight period: May 11–July 24.

Tropidia scita (Harris, 1780)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂, 9 ♀ from three localities (7, 29, 32).

Flight period: May 20–July 06.

Volucella bombylans (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 10 ♂, 5 ♀ from four localities (7, 13, 32, 36).

Flight period: May 11–July 05.

Volucella inanis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 5 ♀ from six localities (7, 25, 29, 30, 32, 37).

Flight period: July 17–August 31.

Volucella inflata (Fabricius, 1794)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂, 17 ♀ from four localities (7, 12, 32, 34).

Flight period: May 17–July 03.

Volucella pellucens (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 8 ♂, 8 ♀ from five localities (5, 7, 13, 32, 36).

Flight period: May 19–September 06.

Volucella zonaria (Poda, 1761)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 11 ♀ from four localities (7, 22, 30, 32).

Flight period: June 04–September 03.

Xanthandrus comtus (Harris, 1780)

Kryshtal, 1949; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 8 ♀ from five localities (7, 11, 29, 30, 32).

Flight period: April 20–November 09.

Xanthogramma citrofasciatum (De Geer, 1776)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 1 ♂, 1 ♀ from two localities (7, 29).

Flight period: April 28–May 11.

Xanthogramma dives (Rondani, 1857)

Prokhorov et al., 2020 b; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 22 ♂, 12 ♀ from six localities (7, 13, 29, 32, 33, 42).

Flight period: May 01–September 16.

Xanthogramma laetum (Fabricius, 1794)

Material examined. Myhalky env. (32), 50.6549, 29.4952, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest and old felling in mixed forest, 22.05.2023, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: May 22.

Remarks. The only studied specimen of *X. laetum* from the Kyiv Region. The species was known only from the Carpathians and Rivne Region.

Xanthogramma pedisequum (Harris, 1778)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂, 6 ♀ from five localities (7, 15, 25, 30, 32).

Flight period: May 28–August 31.

Xanthogramma stackelbergi Violovitsh, 1975

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂, 4 ♀ from four localities (7, 12, 33, 34).

New data: Kodra env. (12), 50.6306, 29.4870, mixed forest, roadside, 14–25.07.2023, *Quercus rubra* leaves (with honey dew), 3 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: June 11–August 23.

Xylota abiens Wiedemann in Meigen, 1822

Prokhorov et al., 2017 b (*caeruleiventris*: misidentification of the female); Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 12 ♂, 3 ♀ from five localities (7, 15, 28, 30, 32).

Flight period: May 18–July 13.

Xylota caeruleiventris Zetterstedt, 1838

Prokhorov et al., 2017 b; Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 2 ♂ from one locality (36).

Flight period: May 21.

Remarks. The first verified record of the species from Ukraine.

Xylota florum (Fabricius, 1805)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 6 ♀ from two localities (28, 32).

Flight period: May 19–August 05.

Xylota jakutorum Bagatshanova, 1980

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 3 ♂, 1 ♀ from two localities (32, 36).

New data: Myhalky env. (32): 50.654, 29.4908, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest, 25.05.2024, 1 ♀; 50.6533, 29.4849, Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 06.09.2024, 1 ♂ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: May 24–September 06.

Xylota meigeniana Stackelberg, 1964

Material examined. Myhalky env. (32): 50.6547, 29.4900, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 04.06.2023, 2 ♂; 50.6517, 29.4886, edge of mixed forest and swampy floodplain forest with *Alnus glutinosa*, 01.07.2023, 1 ♂; 50.6537, 29.4863, edge of Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 19.07.2023, 1 ♀; 50.6533, 29.4849, Teteriv River floodplain forest (along the channel), 20.07.2024, 1 ♀ (A. Prokhorov).

Flight period: June 04–July 20.

Remarks. The first verified record of the species from Ukraine.

Xylota segnis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Stackelberg, 1925 (*Zelima*); Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 6 ♂, 5 ♀ from three localities (13, 25, 32).

Flight period: April 12–October 16.

Xylota sylvarum (Linnaeus, 1758)

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 3 ♀ from three localities (7, 29, 32).

Flight period: May 19–August 10.

Xylota tarda Meigen, 1822

Prokhorov, 2023.

Material examined. 4 ♂, 4 ♀ from three localities (29, 32, 42).

Flightperiod: May 22–September 13.

Conclusion

Before our study, according to literary data, only 37 species of hoverflies were mentioned for the Kyiv Region. The very first careful and targeted collecting of the hoverflies in the Kyiv Region from 2015 to 2024 results in extending the list of species in seven times now represented by 258 species. Five listed species, *Chrysotoxum intermedium* Meigen, 1822, *C. lineare* (Zetterstedt, 1819), *Eristalis abusiva* Collin, 1931, *Meliscaeva cinctella* (Zetterstedt, 1843) and *Platycheirus clypeatus* Meigen, 1822, have not yet been confirmed by collection material. A possible number of species inhabiting the Kyiv Region is provisionally estimated at 270; for comparison, the well-studied syrphid fauna of the Netherlands includes 347 species (Zeegers et al., 2024), and that of Lower Saxony includes 333 species (Stucke, 2019); both are the best-studied territories in Europe, correspondingly 1.5–1.7 times as large as that of the Kyiv Region, and are somewhat more diverse in biotopes and better studied. Given the very uneven exploration of the region, it is hoped that new and interesting discoveries will be made in the future.

Acknowledgments

The authors are grateful to all colleagues who collected hoverflies in the Kyiv Region, and we especially thank Vitaly Kavurka (Institute of Zoology, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv) for his help in providing some articles necessary for the work. The authors also thank Valery Korneyev (Institute of Zoology, NAS of Ukraine, Kyiv) for his valuable scientific and editorial comments.

REFERENCES

- Kryshtal, O. P. 1949. *Materials to the Middle Dnipro River valley entomofauna study. Part. 1. Entomofauna of herbaceous vegetation.* Kyiv, 1–249. (In Ukrainian: Криштал, О. П. Матеріали до вивчення ентомофауни долини Середнього Дніпра. Частина 1. Ентомофауна трав'янистої рослинності. Київ: КДУ ім. Т. Г. Шевченка)
- Nielsen, T. R. 2004. European species of the *Platycheirus ambiguus* group (Diptera, Syrphidae), with description of new species. *Volucella*, 7: 1–30.
- Nielsen, T. R. 2014. Synopsis of the *Platycheirus ambiguus* species group (Diptera, Syrphidae), with description of *Platycheirus arnei* sp. n. and a preliminary key to the species. *Norwegian Journal of Entomology*, 61: 57–75.
- Prokhorov, A. 2023. *Syrphidae (Diptera, Brachycera) collection of the I.I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology NAS of Ukraine.* I.I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology. Occurrence dataset. <https://doi.org/10.15468/ps7637> accessed via GBIF.org on 2023-09-02.
- Prokhorov, A. V. & Popov, G. V. 2017. The first records of *Eristalis picea* (Diptera: Syrphidae) from Ukraine and comparison with *E. obscura*. *Ukrainska Entomofaunistyka*, 8 (2): 11–15.
- Prokhorov, A. V. & Shparyk, V. Yu. 2019. Rare species of hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae), recommended for inclusion in the Red Book of Ukraine. *Ukrainska Entomofaunistyka*,

- 10 (1): 7–12. (In Ukrainian: Прохоров, О. В. і Шпарик, В. Ю. Рідкісні види мух-повисюх (Diptera: Syrphidae), рекомендовані до занесення в Червону книгу України. *Українська ентомофауністика*, 2019, 10 (1): 7–12)
- Prokhorov, A. V., Popov, G. V. & Zaika, M. I. 2017 a. The first records of *Melangyna lucifera* (Diptera: Syrphidae) from Ukraine. *Ukrainska Entomofaunistyka*, 8 (1): 16.
- Prokhorov, A. V., Popov, G. V. & Zaika, M. I. 2017 b. Rare species of hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae) from Ukraine. I. Eristalinae and Syrphinae. *Ukrainska Entomofaunistyka*, 8 (2): 33–39.
- Prokhorov, A. V., Popov, G. V. & Zaika, M. I. 2018 a. New records of hoverflies (Diptera, Syrphidae) from Ukraine. I. Milesiini and Rhingiini. *Vestnik zoologii*, 52 (1): 13–20.
- Prokhorov, A. V., Popov, G. V. & Zaika, M. I. 2018 b. New records of hoverflies (Diptera, Syrphidae) from Ukraine. II. Brachyopini and Merodontini. *Vestnik zoologii*, 52 (2): 125–136.
- Prokhorov, A. V., Popov, G. V. & Zaika, M. I. 2018 c. New records of hoverflies (Diptera, Syrphidae) from Ukraine. III. Pipizinae and Syrphinae. *Vestnik zoologii*, 52 (3): 241–250.
- Prokhorov, A. V., Popov, G. V. & Zaika, M. I. 2018 d. Rare species of hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae) from Ukraine. II. Callicerini, Cerioidini and Milesiini. *Ukrainska Entomofaunistyka*, 9 (2): 15–22.
- Prokhorov, A. V., Popov, G. V. & Shparyk, V. Yu. 2020 a. New records of hoverflies (Diptera, Syrphidae) from Ukraine. IV. *Zoodiversity*, 54 (1): 17–30. <https://doi.org/10.15407/zoo2020.01.017>
- Prokhorov, A. V., Popov, G. V., Shparyk, V. Yu. & Vasilyeva, Yu. S. 2020 b. New records of hoverflies (Diptera, Syrphidae) from Ukraine. V. *Zoodiversity*, 54 (3): 237–258. <https://doi.org/10.15407/zoo2020.03.237>
- Prokhorov, A. V., Popov, G. V., Shparyk, V. Yu. & Vasilyeva, Yu. S. 2023. New records of hoverflies (Diptera, Syrphidae) from Ukraine. VI. *Zoodiversity*, 57 (2): 125–142. <https://doi.org/10.15407/zoo2023.02.125>
- Speight, M. C. D. 2020. *Species accounts of European Syrphidae, 2020. Syrph the Net, the database of European Syrphidae (Diptera)*: 1–314. (Syrph the Net publications, Dublin, 104.)
- Stackelberg, A. A. 1925. Kurze Übersicht der paläarktischen *Zelima* (= *Xylota*) Arten (Dipt., Syrph.). (Aus dem Zoologischen Museum der Russischen Akademie der Wissenschaften). *Deutsche entomologische Zeitschrift*, 4: 279–288.
- Stackelberg, A. A. 1955. Palaearctic species of the genus *Penthesilea* Mg. (Diptera, Syrphidae). *Entomologicheskoe obozrenie*, 34: 340–349. (In Russian: Штакельберг, А. А. Палеарктические виды рода *Penthesilea* Mg. (Diptera, Syrphidae). *Энтомологическое обозрение*, 1955, 34: 340–349)
- Stackelberg, A. A. 1958. The materials on the dipterans fauna of Leningrad Region. IV. Syrphidae (Diptera). *The Proceedings of Zoological Institute, Academy of Science of USSR*, 24: 192–246 (The materials on investigation a fauna and ecology of insects of Leningrad Region). (In Russian: Штакельберг, А. А. Материалы по фауне двукрылых Ленинградской области. IV. Syrphidae (Diptera). В кн.: *Материалы по изучению фауны и экологии насекомых Ленинградской области*. Труды зоологического института, Том 24, Москва–Ленинград: изд-во АН СССР, 1958: 192–246)
- Stackelberg, A. A. 1959. The Palaearctic species of the genus *Chrysogaster* Mg. (Diptera, Syrphidae). *Entomologicheskoe obozrenie*, 38 (4): 898–904. (In Russian: Штакельберг, А. А. Палеарктические виды рода *Chrysogaster* Mg. (Diptera, Syrphidae). *Энтомологическое обозрение*, 1959, 38 (4): 898–904)
- Stackelberg, A. A. 1965. New data on the systematics of Palaearctic hoverflies (Diptera, Syrphidae). *Entomologicheskoe obozrenie*, 44 (4): 907–926. (In Russian: Штакельберг, А. А. Новые данные по систематике палеарктических мух-журчалок (Diptera, Syrphidae). *Энтомологическое обозрение*, 1965, 44 (4): 907–926)
- Stackelberg, A. A. & Richter, V. A. 1968. The materials on the hoverflies (Diptera, Syrphidae) fauna of Caucasus. *The Proceedings of All-Union Entomological Society*, 52 (Insects of Caucasus): 224–274. (In Russian: Штакельберг, А. А. и Рихтер, В. А. Материалы

- по фауне мух-журчалок (Diptera, Syrphidae) Кавказа. В кн.: Бей-Биенко, Г. Я. (гл. ред.), *Насекомые Кавказа. Труды Всесоюзного энтомологического общества*. Том 52, Ленинград: Наука, 1968: 224–274)
- Stucke, J.-H. 2019. Die Fliegen und Mücken Niedersachsens und Bremens — eine Zusammenstellung der bislang publizierten Arten (Insecta, Diptera). *Studia dipterologica. Supplement*, 22: 1–308.
- Violovitsh, N. A. 1960. The materials on the hoverfly (Diptera, Syrphidae) fauna of the Sakhalin and the Kuril Islands. *Proceedings of the All-Union Entomological Society*, 47: 217–272. (In Russian: Виолович, Н. А. Материалы по фауне мух-журчалок (Diptera, Syrphidae) Сахалина и Курильских островов. В кн.: Павловский, Е. Н. (гл. ред.), *Труды Всесоюзного энтомологического общества*. 47, Москва–Ленинград: изд-во АН СССР, 1960: 217–272)
- Zaika, M. I., Korneyev, V. O. & Popov, G. V. 2011. The new records of *Psarus abdominalis* (Diptera: Syrphidae) included in Red Data Book of Ukraine. *Ukrainska Entomofaunistyka*, 2 (5): 16. (In Ukrainian: Заїка, М. І., Корнеєв, В. О. і Попов, Г. В. Нові знахідки псаруса черевастого *Psarus abdominalis* (Diptera: Syrphidae), занесеного до «Червоної книги України». *Українська ентомофауністика*, 2011, 2 (5): 16)
- Zeegers, T., van Steenis, W., Reemer, M. & Smit, J. T. 2024. Drastic acceleration of the extinction rate of hoverflies (Diptera: Syrphidae) in the Netherlands in recent decades, contrary to wild bees (Hymenoptera: Anthophila). *Journal van Syrphidae*, 3 (1): 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.55710/1/YDSJ1547>

Прохоров, О. В., Васильєва, Ю. С.

Інститут зоології ім. І.І. Шмальгаузена НАН України,
вул. Богдана Хмельницького, 15, Київ, 01054, Україна

¹E-mail: al.val.prokhorov@gmail.com

¹<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3367-260X>

МУХИ-ПОВИСЮХИ (DIPTERA, SYRPHIDAE) КИЇВСЬКОЇ ОБЛАСТІ УКРАЇНИ

Вперше проведено спеціальне дослідження мух-повисюх у Київській області України. Подано посилання на опубліковану літературу, відомості про вивчений фактичний матеріал із 42 місцезнаходжень та період льоту сирфід у цьому регіоні. Всього на Київщині зареєстровано 258 види, з яких тільки п'ять видів не підтверджено фактично зібраним матеріалом.

Ключові слова: Україна, мухи-повисюхи, анований лист.